

1 Cdy12 controls resistance behaviors and specifies tumor lineage in human breast cancer.

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7 CDYL2 was isolated as a lineage specifying factor in human breast cancer. In a genome-wide association
8 to identify positions in the genome most significantly correlated with molecular subtype, we identified
9 multiple, discrete single nucleotide polymorphisms in CDYL2 that were among the positions in the genome
10 most significantly associated with the luminal A subtype in humans with breast cancer.

11 Separate from lineage choice, indicating the importance of the imprinting system early in oncogenesis, we
12 isolated CDYL2 as a component of the resistance signaling to chemotherapy in vitro in whole
13 transcriptome expression screens that describe the transcriptional response to two independent
14 chemotherapeutic agents: an endocrine therapy (ET) agent and doxorubicin, demonstrating that in
15 addition to a function for CDYL2 in transformation, it also controlled adaptive behaviors by the tumor in
16 response to clinical interventions. CDYL2 controls PAM50 molecular subtype fate and resistance
17 responses in humans with breast cancer.

18 Citations

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